

Respective quality structure in Albanian education system and priorities in state administrative management

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Abstract: In fact this research is based on national educational system with people is a prerequisite for the economic growth and sustainable development of the country. First and foremost the reform of the educational system needs support, while implementing the governmental initiatives as they aim to have the stable growth, reduction of poverty and the re-dimensioning of the social problems shown in advance. The aim of this paper is to meet the domestic needs of a labor market as they adequate skills for future Albanian citizens with proper knowledge in all social-scientific fields able to face the real life. The socio-cultural aspirations of the people are committed to the implementation of the economic and national plan development. The results or conclusions has to do with centralized management level in the national governance and in the area of service in particular that leads to the reduction of effectiveness and efficiency of public administration. As such is seen as effective one, the re-dimensioning of decentralization, which has marked significant progress in several sectors, including education sectors and responsibilities over it.

Keyword: national education, educational research, self -evaluation, qualitative management, public administration, university strategies

Method: The methodology is empirical one, which means that is used the survey method by collecting data and the results are based on answers from students of Vlore University "Ismail Qemali" and a private college "Pavaresia", which were in verge of graduation and some other unemployed students of different cultures including Erasmus+ students which have completed their work application not only in Albania, but also in many countries abroad like Croatia, Greece, Portugal, Italy and Montenegro.

Objective: state administration's activities are generally managed by Ministry of Education and Science Authorities such as Ministry of Education determine the education policy also in provincial or municipal authorities who take care of citizens in the field of education are fulfilled. Ministry of Education and Science legal power is based on law implementation, other regulations on management and professional supervision approved from parliament and Albanian Government. This ratio of

individual performance evaluation with the respective structure for a significant future career, not only in the success of the administration but also as a guarantee of qualitative management in advance.

Introduction: During such a difficult period of 1990-2000 the administration completely politicized and there were no clear point of view (not to say separation) between the political system and techno-professional functions. The role of the Albanian state was a system and specifically the education system was nearly new role of the state which determined new obligations for the public, central and local administration. The optional curriculum activities and creation of extramural activities in primary school are still in procedure. Also, in order to enhance Futurologist instruction for Information Technology is also required enhancement of regulations on the required qualification degrees of teachers, etc., some legal acts are in preparation, or already completed. The political model control was inappropriate and it was under circumstances of distortion. As such, time demanded development as the only way to come out of these crises and was stimulated to economic improvement and to conceal somehow social injustice in the concept for the interpretation of legal norms on this subject. Nevertheless, the aforementioned legal concept is generally considered problematic, the interpretation of which has led to numerous international disputes.

1. The national education system strategies on university education stipulates

The institutional quality and the enhancement of future Education, a new strategy on universities stipulates and a center of accreditation is being created and is on work, nowadays.

The reforms goals are: to introduce certain innovations adapted to the achievements in science, technique and technology, changes in social relations, laws, etc. New Schools programs on Information Technology, Computing and Informatics are on application of the computer technique in creating vocational subjects in vocational schools and better equipping of schools with computers has been required.

The politicization of the administration ended and it was marked by the year 1999 and the division between the political and techno-professional was a

clear point. The Institution of Training for the Public Administration was funded in order to give response to all the circumstances.

The strategy includes school education, primary and secondary education, general secondary education and professional education. The Decision of the Minister's Council no.657 in 16.09.96 "For ethical rules in the public service", law no. 8549 in 11.11.1999 "The status of the civil employee" shows new opportunities and to the new challenges of the time.

Changes in the vision indicated by National Strategy on University Education, attitudes and conduct of all committed stakeholders are bound to this reform which goes beyond institutional improvements. Until the year 2014 -2015 The National Strategy on University Education stipulates short-term and mid-term goals for the system and introduces policies on strategic priorities. The public administration performance concept of evaluation must be considered as a psycho-social and administrative process which has its own impacts) imported copy/pasted into template are not acceptable.

1.1 The policies and the process of implementing

On pre-university education laws the school managing bodies and their competence are defined by the school board and the school principal.

After the decisions is made by such authorities on school activities, announces open competitions to fill the position of school teachers, and gives opinions on candidates for teachers and school principal. Appointed by the Education Local Authorities the school principal manages the school and His authorizations and responsibility refer to the overall scope of school work through the whole education process.

By such authorizations and responsibility the school, organizes the realization of the annual whole education process, realizes instructional insight in and supervision of the teachers' and professional associates' work, handles the promotion of educational work, undertakes measures against inappropriate behavior of teachers and associates, convenes the sessions of teachers' councils, directs the work of professional bodies and co-operates with the community and everybody in connection with the school. Such followed policies are assigned working students of long term

2. University performance quality and development strategies priorities

The leadership role is based on rules and extreme strict responsibilities toward the students all the working students in University auditorium, learning, expressing innovative ideas, conducting their project in their classes, in order to show up their achievement during this process that involves everything. Teaching methodology, this process of implementing this strategy, the leadership role is based on rules and extreme strict responsibilities toward the students, in order to handle the unexpected difficulties and obstacles the work of all the students to achieve their goals and purposes. (De Bruijn & H.Henglenn 2002) However,

"there are many instances in which a producer can affect quality" so as to influence the customers' product experience (Tirole 1996, Ferrier, Smith, and Grimm 1999; Willard and Cooper 1985).

The development strategies given by the teacher and the evaluation of student scientific projects are the main development trends of education in Europe and in the world, aiming to adopt the development of university education to the governmental vision for mid-term and long-term policies. It incorporates the suggestions of the academic community and of the groups of interest within the country. Some analytical models in the industrial organization literature allow firms to select quality in each period and evaluate its effect on the price premium required to maintain its quality "reputation" (Klein and Leffler 1981; Shapiro 1983). These studies assume a fixed "one time-period" information lag for customers while acknowledging the impact of varying. The strategy represents the new era development with tasks scheduled to be implemented. Most marketing studies on brand choice assume that quality is constant over time (Jedidi et al. 1999; Mela et al. 1997)

3. Literature review

Often in everyday life student-teacher relationship is mutual and the leadership responsibility is high. Depending on such difficulties and responsibilities that the duty takes, fundamental is to be perceived as such the relationship which are characterized by tolerant communications that runs through good will of understanding and by tolerance. Learning process is difficult, but if someone (students themselves) is not given what is meant hard to resolve, human being never knows how far reaches. Cultural differences on these dimensions could be described as multi-polar dimensions allows us to make some predictions on the way their society operates, including their management processes and the kind of theories applicable to educational system, based on their lifestyle. In my theoretical point of view culture distribute a background knowledge unknown to the same human being but of different nation. To such extent, there is a rich tradition in the literature that studies this reputation-building process through the determinants and dynamics of perceived quality. They are construction or bonds that should not be reified. An important aspect of our daily work and educational learning, where there should be tolerance and to show the full comprehension, the superlative degree is that of controlling student knowledge gained through time.

According to this literature, perceived quality is determined primarily by prior goal quality and prior expectations of quality. In my statistical analysis of empirical data.

4. Analyzing data

The methodology is empirical one, which means that is used by surveying and collecting all the data and the results based on the answers from the students of Vlora University "Ismail Qemali" and another private college called "Pavaresia" or (*Indipence*), which were in verge of their Graduation and some other unemployed students of different culture, which have completed their work application not only in Albania, but also in many countries abroad like Croatia, Greece, Portugal, Montenegro,

Educational Ability leadership	Personal management to offer a modern educational service	Financial planning and managing	Results
Knowledge	Re-Dimensioning and modernize the curricula	Practice built on knowledge	40-50%
Students Graduated	Trying to be the best	Not able to manage s.m.th right	70-90%
Under-Graduated Students	We are all the same	Different life circumstances of every student in world, not able to get diploma	60%
University	Assure students with scientific knowledge and laboratories 'practice	Support process in all its factors and aspects	80-100%
Different culture background and multi-cultural influence	Have more options in proceeding with the management process	They plan their incomes and also the improvement of personal lifestyle	60-65%
Science and life	They who know to use professional training in decision-making can manage life and propel	a) They who know how to use the scientific method they can get the incomes financially b) can be successful	70% 30%

Italy.

In the graph below are in a comparison of the values of similar people (employed -unemployed) in different Corporation worldwide. The interviewed students are graduated, non-graduated in the same training program which represent every well-matched samples from the populations of their countries and also from countries with different cultural background.

The graphs level has two ways the first has to do with the right contemporaneous students graduated in their proper time and the second way has to do with prior expectations of quality of the students trained in such programs which represents new challenges for the time. (Boulding et al. 1993) the authors first test this model with data from a longitudinal laboratory experiment. Then they develop a method for estimating the model with one-time survey data, and re-estimate the model using such data collected in a field study. Empirical findings from the two tests of the model indicate, among other things, that the two different types of expectations have opposing effects on perceptions of service quality and that service quality perceptions positively affect intended behaviors.). Culture is a construction that means it is "as if it is not accessible to survey, it is an auxiliary concept that should be used as long as it is tested as useful when the results are expected but useful when the results are not satisfactory.

The estimated results is mainly characterized by qualitative indicators and there are only a few quantitative indicators. Analyzing the data collected from the questionnaires the employees and students asses the importance of the performance evaluation in 100%,

"Depending on different culture or nation is the performance fair in your institution?"- 28% answered positively, 59% avoided the answer and 23% of them think differently.

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5. Performance quality of university educational system and the outcomes

The Performance Quality of University Education System is mainly shown by qualitative indicators and then the quantitative indicators are afterwards. Based on to the data analyzed from the questionnaires the students, employees, teachers asses the importance of the performance evaluation in 100%, they show it as it follows. "Depending on different culture or nation is the performance fair in your institution?"- 28% answered positively, 59% avoided the answer and 23% of them think differently According to the questionnaire the major part of the questioned the students, employees, teachers think that the performance Quality of University Education System it has a conflict between the staff and the superiors in position as leaders.

Regardless to what is written above the consequences as well as results have failed to meet the needs and requirements of the community of

- a) Educational leadership,
- b) School management, contenting of curricula,
- c) Financial planning and management,
- e) School maintenance,
- f) Personnel management to offer a modern educational service and discharge the integrating function of schools.

With all the consequences in respect of the malfunctioning the Reform and strengthening of policy making, management and decision making capacity is one of the priorities

In the framework of the International partnership of education according to which: "The government is committed to realize the school autonomy through the educational reform in cooperation with the groups of interest" The European commission International partnership of education with life-long approach in higher education ,technical vocational, research and mobility are guided by key principles of equity and inclusion: Albania has followed these important steps and it aim to fill the gap in qualified teachers, so that the young people can confidently create and take up jobs in context in the era of digital transition.

The European Union is the main investor in education worldwide. It dedicates to global education in a life-long learning approach more than 10% of its International Partnerships budget, over €6 billion. This figure is an estimate for the 2021-2027 period. (Taken from European commission International partnership)

The Albanian University Education System has come out from an Old Russian system of school conspiracy. Meanwhile, it remains relevant to discuss whether system has the same priorities or not.

Are the directions of the priorities of the economic sectors harmonized with the directions of the financial system?

If the answer were yes, this would be evidence to a development and progress in the right direction. If not, we need to make the necessary adjustments. While leadership researchers have emphasized that managers need to vary the performance of their leadership functions depending on characteristics of their followers, the task, the organizational culture, their position power, and other factors, they have commonly equated followers with subordinates.

The outcomes research presented in this paper has taken a distinctly different approach and examined the leadership behaviors of two groups of managers in their interactions with the members of their superiors and peers, in addition to their subordinates.

In the paper are taken many groups to be examined but in the focus was the interaction with the subordinates, new graduate and under-graduate teacher their financial managing in order to be effective leaders in their interactions with their subordinates, peers, and superiors.

The ability can vary the performance of these leadership, they can broad repertoire of leadership functions, because they need to have at their disposal, as well as well-functioning depends on the school. Universities, organizations or corporates in which the person interact in daily life basis.

6. Conclusions

The University Education System guidance in terms of EU development framework represent a

View to be developed in accordance with the current standards. Decentralization of the system and service was the key base component for the broader decentralization process undertaken in Albania.

The application of a too centralized management level in the national governance in general and in the area of services in particular, leads to the reduction of effectiveness and efficiency of the public administration.

Re-dimensioning the decentralization has marked significant progress in several sectors, including the sector of education, the progress of the decentralization of responsibilities and of the decision making authority from central to local level for the pre-university education has not been satisfactory in giving the right performance of Albanian University

There exist a gap of school operational bond to community including the cultural differences as a democratic approach in providing effective education to all. Is being notified a lack of encouragement from family to fully invest efforts in the area of education Regardless to what is written above the consequences as well as results have failed to meet the needs and requirements of the community of a) Educational leadership, b) School management, contenting of curricula, c) Financial planning and management, e) School maintenance, f) Personnel management to offer a modern educational service and discharge the integrating function of schools.

With all the consequences in respect of the malfunctioning the Reform and strengthening of policy making, management and decision making capacity is one of the priorities

The priorities should be focused on Albania regions by Re-dimensioning Educational Directorates and Educational Offices by further developing capacities in support of schools. It also should be focused on school autonomy themselves in the area of subject programs, financing, personnel and management at school level and above, completing it with the legal basis and respective implementation. And responsible for this is Ministry of Education and Science and subordinate institutions by building a clear management performance within 3-5 years developing policies and launching of research based on functioning of the information management system in the area of education not only in central schools and universities but also in local schools.

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